

REQUIREMENTS FOR STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions and comments about the requirements for students' knowledge of musical instrument performance in music culture lessons.

Key words: Music culture, instrument performance, rubob, art, note, octave.

The rich music created by our wise people is our great spiritual wealth, and it is considered an invaluable resource for the moral and ideological aesthetic education of the young generation. Because the baby begins to perceive the most elegant and relaxing folk music - the mother's alla - when he is lying in the cradle, even before his tongue comes out. Therefore, folk music is the closest form of art to the human heart. That is why folk music is given a special place in the music programs of general secondary schools of our Republic. It requires that the materials of folk music be included in the annual educational materials of each class. Because the creation of folk music is the basis of professional music, and every composer can create a high-quality and multi-voiced work only as a result of appropriate use of folk music styles and elegant melodies. The proof of this is that the major and minor scales in modern music, which are common to all nations, were formed only as a result of the high level of development of folk music lessons and were settled with the advent of classical music.

In musical culture classes, it is planned to learn the requirements for students' knowledge of musical instruments in the form of practical training. For effective training, it is recommended to use folk instruments, posters, music recordings of musical groups or orchestras, musical scores as visual aids. Taking into account that students' musical knowledge is different, it is necessary to pay attention to the correct assignment of tasks for independent training.

It is known that most of the instruments of Uzbek folk instruments are widely distributed in other nations and have been kept in this state or in a slightly changed state. When mastering the topic of the history of musical instruments, it will be useful to provide more complete information about such musical instruments. During the period when instruments are studied separately, it is a relief for students to study the tuning or range of each instrument depending on the aspects of similarity to some other instrument. For example, the tuning of

double bass double strings is the opposite of the tuning of prima rubob strings, that is, if the strings of rubob prima are tuned to the sounds of sol, re, lya, mi, and the double bass strings are tuned to the sounds of mi, lya, re, sol. It is recommended to make good use of similar aspects even during the period when ranges are mastered. For example, it is not news for experts that instruments belonging to the group of mezrob instruments have 2-octave and 1.5-octave scales. If prima rubobi, kashgar rubobi, alto dutori and bass dutori are considered to be 2 octaves, Afghan rubobi and contrabass dutori are considered to be one and a half octaves. Therefore, the open tone of the thinnest strings of instruments with a 2-octave scale is the same as the last highest note in the range of these instruments. For example, mi in the prima rubob, and lya in other instruments. When the instruments are being mastered separately, it is good to organize classes in the form of conversation and communication with the students who are learning this instrument.

To the extent possible, it is necessary to strengthen theoretical information with visual aids and practical tasks. In the process of mastering the subject of "Instrumental Studies", students learn about the types of Uzbek national musical instruments, historical information about them, the tuning, range, performance possibilities and characteristics of each musical instrument, as well as their use in musical ensembles. It is planned to receive information such as the secrets of sounding well when played with which instruments. It is necessary to get the student to know by heart the possibilities of Uzbek folk musical instruments (tuning, range and performance bars). In order to have a sufficient idea of each musical instrument, it is desirable that the instrument being studied be demonstrated and the levels of possibility demonstrated by practical performance.

In order to avoid difficulties and misunderstandings during training in the subject of "Instrumentation", the student must thoroughly learn information about transposable musical instruments and musical keys. In the process of organizing lessons in the subject of "Instrumental Studies", the students' theoretical knowledge and practical experience in the subjects "Piano", "Special Instrument", "Music Theory", "Orchestral Class", "Ensemble Class" 'skills will help. In turn, the knowledge gained in the subject of "Instrumental Studies" creates a foundation for mastering a number of subjects such as "Instrumentation", "Learning folk instruments", "Reading sheet music".

It is known that any piece of music is a work of art. Its performance at the level of an artistic work requires thorough knowledge and high skill from the

musician. A teacher should be able to instill in him a love for this instrument while training a future musician. For this, it is necessary to constantly include works that sound well on this instrument and that are liked by the student in the pedagogical repertoire. When working on works, attention should be paid to mastering each line and creating a good sound from the beginning. Because the strength and quality of the sound in the musician is one of the main criteria for the artistic expression of the performance.

Artistic expression is important in the performance of the kashkar rubob instrument. No matter how high the performance technique of the composer is, if he cannot reveal the artistic features of the work, he cannot leave a good impression on the listener. Such a work will have a lifeless, soulless, simple appearance. For this, the musician should know his instrument well and master the expressive features of the lines, be able to use them as needed, and be able to create a clear, melodious, collected sound and be able to control it. should be.

As we continue to implement music education in general secondary schools, the teacher has the task of arousing students' interest in their lesson and music. The interest and inclination towards singing and listening to music at school plays an important role in the development and formation of young people's positive attitudes towards art and other needs.

A music lesson is an art lesson by its very nature. Making it colorful, rich and interesting requires great pedagogical and professional skills from every teacher. "It is extremely difficult to teach children to art," says the well-known composer and musicologist scientist D.B. Kabalevsky.

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